

On Legendre Cordial Labeling of Some Graphs Under Graph Operations

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Abstract

For a simple connected graph G of order n , a bijective function $f : V(G) \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ is said to be a Legendre cordial labeling modulo p , where p is an odd prime, if the induced function $f_p^* : E(G) \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$, defined by $f_p^*(uv) = 0$ whenever $([f(u) + f(v)]/p) = -1$ or $f(u) + f(v) \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$, and $f_p^*(uv) = 1$ whenever $([f(u) + f(v)]/p) = 1$, satisfies the condition $|e_{f_p^*}(0) - e_{f_p^*}(1)| \leq 1$ where $e_{f_p^*}(i)$ is the number of edges with label i ($i = 0, 1$). This paper investigates the Legendre cordial labeling of graphs obtained through various operations: join, corona, lexicographic product, cartesian product, tensor product, and strong product.

Keywords: odd prime, Legendre cordial labeling, Legendre cordial graph

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1 Introduction

All graphs considered in this paper are finite, simple, and connected. A graph $G = (V, E)$ has a vertex set $V = V(G)$ and an edge set $E = E(G)$, and the cardinalities $|V|$ and $|E|$ are called the order and size of G , respectively. In addition, the elements of V and E are called vertices and edges, respectively. For further graph-theoretic definitions and properties, refer to [6].

Mathematics often evolves from simple ideas that grow into powerful tools for understanding the world. Graph theory, for example, began with a puzzle in 1736 when Euler solved the famous Königsberg bridge problem. This laid the groundwork for representing networks using vertices and edges. Over time, graph theory became a key part of computer science, transportation planning, biology, and social networks.

One important concept in graph theory is *graph labeling*, in which numbers or labels are assigned to the vertices, the edges, or both of a graph following specific conditions. Graph labeling has applications in communication systems, coding theory, circuit design, and frequency assignment.

Rosa [9] introduced several important types of graph labeling, known as α -, β -, σ -, and ρ -valuations, which laid the foundation for many forms of graph labeling studied today. One of these, the β -valuation (also known as *graceful labeling*), applies to a graph with q edges: labeling the n vertices with distinct values from $\{0, 1, \dots, q\}$ so that the edge labels, defined as the absolute differences between endpoint labels, are all distinct and range from 1 to q . This becomes particularly useful in network addressing and X-ray crystallography, where unique edge labels prevent interference and overlap.

A specific type of graph labeling known as *cordial labeling*, introduced by Cahit [5] in 1987, extends these ideas in a more accessible form. Inspired by Rosa's graceful labeling, cordial labeling is considered a weaker version of graceful labeling. The idea is to label the

vertices with 0s and 1s so that the resulting edge labels (often derived from vertex labels) are roughly balanced in count. Cordial labeling has given rise to many interesting variants presented in [8].

Number theory, another profound area of mathematics, focuses on the properties of integers. Prime numbers have been studied since ancient times. Euclid proved the infinitude of primes, while Eratosthenes devised the elegant sieve method to generate primes. In modern times, prime numbers play a critical role in cybersecurity, especially through encryption schemes like RSA, which rely on the difficulty of factoring large primes. [10]

The Legendre symbol, introduced by Legendre in the late 18th century, was developed as part of his investigations into quadratic residues and reciprocity, a cornerstone topic in number theory. By definition, an integer a relatively prime to an odd prime p is called a quadratic residue of p if the quadratic congruence $x^2 \equiv a \pmod{p}$ has a solution; otherwise, a is a quadratic nonresidue of p . Thus, the Legendre symbol (a/p) is defined as

$$(a/p) = \begin{cases} -1 & \text{if } a \text{ is a quadratic nonresidue of } p \\ 1 & \text{if } a \text{ is a quadratic residue of } p. \end{cases}$$

One important property of the Legendre symbol is the following: If a and b are integers relatively prime to p (where p is an odd prime) and $a \equiv b \pmod{p}$, then $(a/p) = (b/p)$. For an expanded discussion of the Legendre symbol and its properties, see [4].

The concept of Legendre cordial labeling was first introduced in [3], where it was shown that the path graph P_p , cycle graph C_p , star graph S_p , tadpole graph $T_{p,p}$, kayak paddle graph $KP_{p,p,p}$, bistar graph $B_{p,p}$, and fan graph F_{p+1} all admit a Legendre cordial labeling modulo p , where p is an odd prime. Additionally, the characterization of the Legendre cordial labeling of complete graph K_n has been obtained in [2]. However, no study has been conducted for graphs obtained from graph operations. Thus, this paper explores the Legendre cordial labeling of some graphs obtained from graph operations: join, corona, lexicographic product, cartesian product, tensor product, and strong product.

Let $f : V(G) \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ be a bijective function, where G is a simple connected graph of order n , and let p be an odd prime. Then f is said to be a *Legendre cordial labeling modulo p* if the induced function $f_p^* : E(G) \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$, defined by

$$f_p^*(uv) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } ([f(u) + f(v)]/p) = -1 \text{ or } f(u) + f(v) \equiv 0 \pmod{p} \\ 1 & \text{if } ([f(u) + f(v)]/p) = 1, \end{cases}$$

satisfies the condition $|e_{f_p^*}(0) - e_{f_p^*}(1)| \leq 1$, where $e_{f_p^*}(i)$ denotes the number of edges with label i ($i = 0, 1$). A graph that admits a Legendre cordial labeling modulo p is called a *Legendre cordial graph modulo p* .

2 Basic Concepts

Definition 2.1. A path graph P_n of order n is a graph with vertex set $V(P_n) = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$ and edge set $E(P_n) = \{v_1v_2, v_2v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}v_n\}$.

Definition 2.2. A complete graph K_n of order n is a graph for which each two distinct vertices of K_n are adjacent.

Definition 2.3. A graph G is said to be a bipartite graph if its vertex set $V(G)$ can be partitioned into two non-empty subsets V_1 and V_2 such that every edge of G has one end in V_1 and one end in V_2 .

Definition 2.4. [1, 6, 7] Let G_1 and G_2 be graphs. Note that the vertex set of the graphs defined in items (iii) to (vi) is $V(G_1) \times V(G_2)$.

i. The join graph $G_1 + G_2$ is a graph with vertex set

$$V(G_1 + G_2) = V(G_1) \cup V(G_2)$$

and edge set

$$E(G_1 + G_2) = E(G_1) \cup E(G_2) \cup \{uv : u \in V(G_1) \text{ and } v \in V(G_2)\}.$$

ii. If G_1 has order n , then the corona graph $G_1 \circ G_2$ is a graph obtained by taking one copy of G_1 and n copies of G_2 , and then joining the i th vertex of G_1 to every vertex of the i th copy of G_2 .

iii. The lexicographic product graph $G_1[G_2]$ is a graph with edge set

$$E(G_1[G_2]) = \{(v_1, u_1)(v_2, u_2) : v_1v_2 \in E(G_1), \text{ or } v_1 = v_2 \text{ and } u_1u_2 \in E(G_2)\}.$$

iv. The cartesian product graph $G_1 \square G_2$ is a graph with edge set

$$E(G_1 \square G_2) = \{(v_1, u_1)(v_2, u_2) : v_1 = v_2 \text{ and } u_1u_2 \in E(G_2), \text{ or } u_1 = u_2 \text{ and } v_1v_2 \in E(G_1)\}.$$

v. The tensor product graph $G_1 \times G_2$ is a graph with edge set

$$E(G_1 \times G_2) = \{(v_1, u_1)(v_2, u_2) : v_1v_2 \in E(G_1) \text{ and } u_1u_2 \in E(G_2)\}.$$

vi. The strong product graph $G_1 \boxtimes G_2$ is a graph with edge set

$$E(G_1 \boxtimes G_2) = E(G_1 \square G_2) \cup E(G_1 \times G_2).$$

Theorem 2.1. [11] Let G_1 and G_2 be connected graphs. If G_1 or G_2 has a cycle of odd order, then the tensor product graph $G_1 \times G_2$ is a connected graph.

Theorem 2.2. [4] The odd prime p has $\frac{p-1}{2}$ quadratic residues and $\frac{p-1}{2}$ quadratic nonresidues in the set $\{1, 2, \dots, p-1\}$.

Theorem 2.3. [4, 10] Let p be an odd prime. Then

$$\left(\frac{2}{p}\right) = \begin{cases} -1 & \text{if } p \equiv \pm 3 \pmod{8} \\ 1 & \text{if } p \equiv \pm 1 \pmod{8}. \end{cases}$$

3 Main Results

In the following discussion, p is denoted as an odd prime.

Theorem 3.1. *Let G be a connected graph of order n , $n \geq 2$, and let $p \equiv \pm 3 \pmod{8}$. If G has size n or $n \pm 1$, then the corona graph $G \circ P_{p-1}$ is a Legendre cordial graph modulo p .*

Proof. According to Theorem 2.3, $(2/p) = -1$. Suppose that $V(G) = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$ and $E(G) = \{\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, \dots, \varepsilon_q\}$, $q \in \{n-1, n, n+1\}$. Let P_{p-1}^i denote the i th copy of P_{p-1} with $V(P_{p-1}^i) = \{u_1^i, u_2^i, \dots, u_{p-1}^i\}$, where $u_j^i v_i$ is an edge of $G \circ P_{p-1}$ for $j = 1, 2, \dots, p-1$ and $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$. Let $f : V(G \circ P_{p-1}) \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, np\}$ be a bijective function defined by

$$f(u_j^i) = \begin{cases} j + \frac{p+1}{2} + p(i-1) & \text{for } j = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{p-1}{2} \\ j - \frac{p-1}{2} + p(i-1) & \text{for } j = \frac{p+1}{2}, \frac{p+3}{2}, \dots, p-1, \end{cases}$$

and

$$f(v_i) = \frac{p+1}{2} + p(i-1)$$

for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

For the edges of P_{p-1}^i :

$$f(u_j^i) + f(u_{j+1}^i) \equiv \begin{cases} 2(j+1) \pmod{p} & \text{for } j = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{p-3}{2} \\ [2(j+1) - p] \pmod{p} & \text{for } \frac{p-1}{2}, \frac{p+1}{2}, \dots, p-2 \end{cases}$$

for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$. Given this labeling, for each $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, let

$$\alpha_i = \bigcup_{j=1}^{p-2} \{\xi : f(u_j^i) + f(u_{j+1}^i) \equiv \xi \pmod{p}, 0 < \xi < p\}$$

and consequently,

$$\alpha_i = \{1\} \cup \{3, 4, \dots, p-1\}.$$

By Theorem 2.2, since $(2/p) = -1$ and $2 \notin \alpha_i$, it follows that p has $\frac{p-1}{2}$ quadratic residues and $\frac{p-3}{2}$ quadratic nonresidues in α_i , for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

For the edges of the form $u_j^i v_i$:

$$f(u_j^i) + f(v_i) \equiv (j+1) \pmod{p}, \text{ for } j = 1, 2, \dots, p-2$$

and

$$f(u_{p-1}^i) + f(v_i) \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$$

for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$. In view of this labeling, for each $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, define

$$\beta_i = \bigcup_{j=1}^{p-2} \{\xi : f(u_j^i) + f(v_i) \equiv \xi \pmod{p}, 0 < \xi < p\}.$$

Then

$$\beta_i = \{2, 3, \dots, p-1\}.$$

Since $(1/p) = 1$ and $1 \notin \beta_i$, it follows by Theorem 2.2 that p has $\frac{p-3}{2}$ quadratic residues and $\frac{p-1}{2}$ quadratic nonresidues in β_i , for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$. Moreover, observe that

$$f_p^*(u_{p-1}^i v_i) = 0$$

for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

Lastly, for the edges of G : Because $\varepsilon_k = v_a v_b$, for some $a, b \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$, $a \neq b$, then

$$f(v_a) + f(v_b) \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$$

and it follows that

$$f_p^*(\varepsilon_k) = 1$$

for $k = 1, 2, \dots, q$.

From the above results, we conclude that

$$e_{f_p^*}(0) = n \left(\frac{p-3}{2} \right) + n \left(\frac{p-1}{2} \right) + n$$

and

$$e_{f_p^*}(1) = n \left(\frac{p-1}{2} \right) + n \left(\frac{p-3}{2} \right) + q.$$

Since $q \in \{n-1, n, n+1\}$, we obtain $|e_{f_p^*}(0) - e_{f_p^*}(1)| \leq 1$. Hence, $G \circ P_{p-1}$ is a Legendre cordial graph modulo p . ■

Theorem 3.2. *The tensor product graph $K_p \times G$, where G is a connected bipartite graph, is a Legendre cordial graph modulo p .*

Proof. Let $V(K_p) = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_p\}$ and let m be the size of G . Since G is a bipartite graph, the vertex set $V(G)$ can be partitioned into two non-empty subsets V_1 and V_2 with $V_k = \{u_1^k, u_2^k, \dots, u_{r_k}^k\}$ for $k = 1, 2$. Thus,

$$E(K_p \times G) = \bigcup_{u_x^1 u_y^2 \in E(G)} \{(v_i u_x^1)(v_j u_y^2) : i, j = 1, 2, \dots, p, i \neq j\}.$$

Now, let $f : V(K_p \times G) \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, p(r_1 + r_2)\}$ be a bijective function defined as follows: For $s_k = 1, 2, \dots, r_k$,

$$f((v_t, u_{s_k}^k)) = \begin{cases} t + p(s_1 - 1) & \text{for } k = 1 \text{ and } t = 1, 2, \dots, p \\ p - t + p(s_2 + r_1 - 1) & \text{for } k = 2 \text{ and } t = 1, 2, \dots, p - 1 \\ p + p(s_2 + r_1 - 1) & \text{for } k = 2 \text{ and } t = p. \end{cases}$$

Consequently, for $j = 1, 2, \dots, p$,

$$f((v_j, u_x^1)) + f((v_i, u_y^2)) \equiv \begin{cases} (j - i) \pmod{p} & \text{for } i = 1, 2, \dots, j - 1, \\ (j + p - i) \pmod{p} & \text{for } i = j + 1, j + 2, \dots, p - 1, \\ j \pmod{p} & \text{for } i = p, j \neq p \end{cases}$$

where $u_x^1 u_y^2 \in E(G)$. Given this labeling, for each $j = 1, 2, \dots, p$, define

$$\alpha_{u_x^1 u_y^2}^j = \bigcup_{\substack{i=1 \\ i \neq j}}^p \{\xi : f((v_j, u_x^1)) + f((v_i, u_y^2)) \equiv \xi \pmod{p}, 0 < \xi < p\}$$

where $u_x^1 u_y^2 \in E(G)$. It follows that

$$\alpha_{u_x^1 u_y^2}^j = \{1, 2, \dots, p-1\}$$

for all $j = 1, 2, \dots, p$ and $u_x^1 u_y^2 \in E(G)$. By Theorem 2.2, we have

$$e_{f_p^*}(0) = e_{f_p^*}(1) = mp \binom{p-1}{2}$$

and hence $|e_{f_p^*}(0) - e_{f_p^*}(1)| = 0$. Therefore, $K_p \times G$ is a Legendre cordial graph modulo p . ■

In the following results, let G_1 and G_2 be graphs of orders q_1 and q_2 , respectively. For each $i = 1, 2$, let $g_i : V(G_i) \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, q_i\}$ be a bijective function. Define the following subsets of $E(G_i)$:

$$\varrho_i = \{ab \in E(G_i) : ([g_i(a) + g_i(b)]/p) = 1\} \quad (1)$$

and

$$\eta_i = \{ab \in E(G_i) : ([g_i(a) + g_i(b)]/p) = -1 \text{ or } g_i(a) + g_i(b) \equiv 0 \pmod{p}\} \quad (2)$$

for $i = 1, 2$.

In the case where the range of g_i ($i = 1, 2$) consists of $k_i p$ elements, that is, G_i has order $k_i p$, where k_i is a positive integer, we define the partition of range into subsets

$$\lambda_t^i = \{tp + 1, tp + 2, \dots, tp + p\}$$

for $t = 0, 1, \dots, k_i - 1$. Correspondingly, for each $t = 0, 1, \dots, k_i - 1$, define

$$D_t^i = \{a \in V(G_i) : g_i(a) \in \lambda_t^i\}.$$

Theorem 3.3. *Let G_1 and G_2 be graphs of orders np and m , respectively. If*

$$|\varrho_1| + |\varrho_2| = |\eta_1| + |\eta_2| + nm \pm 1 \quad (3)$$

or

$$|\varrho_1| + |\varrho_2| = |\eta_1| + |\eta_2| + nm, \quad (4)$$

then the join graph $G_1 + G_2$ is a Legendre cordial graph modulo p .

Proof. Let $V(G_1) = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{np}\}$ and $V(G_2) = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_m\}$. Define the bijective function $f : V(G_1 + G_2) \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, np + m\}$ by

$$f(v_i) = g_1(v_i), \text{ for } i = 1, 2, \dots, np$$

and

$$f(u_j) = g_2(u_j) + np, \text{ for } j = 1, 2, \dots, m.$$

For the edges of G_k : If $ab \in E(G_k)$, then

$$f(a) + f(b) \equiv [g_k(a) + g_k(b)](\text{mod } p),$$

which means

$$f_p^*(ab) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } ab \in \eta_k \\ 1 & \text{if } ab \in \varrho_k \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

for each $k = 1, 2$.

For the remaining edges:

$$f(v_i) + f(u_j) \equiv [g_1(v_i) + g_2(u_j)](\text{mod } p) \quad (6)$$

for $i = 1, 2, \dots, np$ and $j = 1, 2, \dots, m$.

Now, for $j = 1, 2, \dots, m$ and $t = 0, 1, \dots, n - 1$, let

$$\alpha_t^j = \bigcup_{a \in D_t^1} \{\xi : f(a) + f(u_j) \equiv \xi(\text{mod } p), 0 \leq \xi < p\}$$

and by (6), it follows that

$$\alpha_t^j = \{0\} \cup \{1, 2, \dots, p - 1\}. \quad (7)$$

In accordance with (5) and (7), and Theorem 2.2, we have

$$e_{f_p^*}(0) = |\eta_1| + |\eta_2| + nm \left(\frac{p-1}{2} \right) + nm$$

and

$$e_{f_p^*}(1) = |\varrho_1| + |\varrho_2| + nm \left(\frac{p-1}{2} \right).$$

By (3) and (4), it is immediate that $|e_{f_p^*}(0) - e_{f_p^*}(1)| \leq 1$, and so $G_1 + G_2$ is a Legendre cordial graph modulo p . ■

Theorem 3.4. *Let G_1 be a connected graph of order n and G_2 be a graph of order mp . If*

$$|\varrho_1| + n|\varrho_2| = |\eta_1| + n|\eta_2| + nm \pm 1 \quad (8)$$

or

$$|\varrho_1| + n|\varrho_2| = |\eta_1| + n|\eta_2| + nm, \quad (9)$$

then the corona graph $G_1 \circ G_2$ is a Legendre cordial graph modulo p .

Proof. Let $V(G_1) = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$ and $V(G_2) = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{mp}\}$. Suppose that G_2^i is denoted as i th copy of G_2 with $V(G_2^i) = \{u_1^i, u_2^i, \dots, u_{mp}^i\}$ for which each vertex of G_2^i is adjacent to v_i , for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$. Now, let $f : V(G_1 \circ G_2) \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, n + nmp\}$ be a bijective function defined by

$$f(u_j^i) = g_2(u_j^i) + mp(i - 1), \text{ for } j = 1, 2, \dots, mp$$

and

$$f(v_i) = g_1(v_i) + nmp$$

for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

For the edges of G_1 : If $ab \in E(G_1)$, then

$$f(a) + f(b) \equiv [g_1(a) + g_1(b)](\text{mod } p)$$

and consequently,

$$f_p^*(ab) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } ab \in \eta_1 \\ 1 & \text{if } ab \in \varrho_1. \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

Similarly, for the edges of G_2^i : If $a^i b^i \in E(G_2^i)$, then

$$f(a^i) + f(b^i) \equiv [g_2(a) + g_2(b)](\text{mod } p)$$

and as a result

$$f_p^*(a^i b^i) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } ab \in \eta_2 \\ 1 & \text{if } ab \in \varrho_2 \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

For the remaining edges:

$$f(v_i) + f(u_j^i) \equiv [g_1(v_i) + g_2(u_j)](\text{mod } p) \quad (12)$$

for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ and $j = 1, 2, \dots, mp$.

Now, for every $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ and $t = 0, 1, \dots, m - 1$, define

$$\alpha_t^i = \bigcup_{a \in D_t^i} \{\xi : f(v_i) + f(a^i) \equiv \xi(\text{mod } p), 0 \leq \xi < p\}$$

and by using (12), we have

$$\alpha_t^i = \{0\} \cup \{1, 2, \dots, p - 1\}. \quad (13)$$

By combining (10), (11), and (13), and applying Theorem 2.2, we obtain

$$e_{f_p^*}(0) = |\eta_1| + n|\eta_2| + nm \left(\frac{p-1}{2} \right) + nm$$

and

$$e_{f_p^*}(1) = |\varrho_1| + n|\varrho_2| + nm \left(\frac{p-1}{2} \right).$$

Thus, (8) and (9) implies that $|e_{f_p^*}(0) - e_{f_p^*}(1)| \leq 1$. Hence, $G_1 \circ G_2$ is a Legendre cordial graph modulo p . ■

Theorem 3.5. *Let G_1 be a connected graph of order n and size n . Also, let G_2 be a graph of order mp . If*

$$|\varrho_2| = |\eta_2| + m^2 p,$$

then the lexicographic product graph $G_1[G_2]$ is a Legendre cordial graph modulo p .

Proof. Let $V(G_1) = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$ and $V(G_2) = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{mp}\}$. So,

$$E(G_1[G_2]) = \bigcup_{xy \in E(G_1)} \{(x, u_i)(y, u_j) : i, j = 1, 2, \dots, mp\}.$$

Suppose that $f : V(G_1[G_2]) \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, nmp\}$ is a bijective function defined by

$$f((v_i, u_j)) = g_2(u_j) + p(i - 1)$$

for $j = 1, 2, \dots, mp$ and $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

For the edges of the form $(v_i, a)(v_i, b)$ where $ab \in E(G_2)$:

$$f((v_i, a)) + f((v_i, b)) \equiv [g_2(a) + g_2(b)](\text{mod } p)$$

and so

$$f_p^*((v_i, a)(v_i, b)) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } ab \in \eta_2 \\ 1 & \text{if } ab \in \varrho_2 \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

For the rest of the edges:

$$f((x, u_j)) + f((y, u_k)) \equiv [g_2(u_j) + g_2(u_k)](\text{mod } p) \quad (15)$$

for $j, k = 1, 2, \dots, mp$ and $xy \in E(G_1)$.

Next, for each $j = 1, 2, \dots, mp$, $t = 0, 1, \dots, m - 1$, and $xy \in E(G_1)$, define the set

$$\alpha_{j,t}^{xy} = \bigcup_{a \in D_t^2} \{\xi : f((x, u_j)) + f((y, a)) \equiv \xi(\text{mod } p), 0 \leq \xi < p\}$$

which, by (15), simplifies to

$$\alpha_{j,t}^{xy} = \{0\} \cup \{1, 2, \dots, p - 1\}. \quad (16)$$

Therefore, using (14) and (16), along with Theorem 2.2, we obtain

$$e_{f_p^*}(0) = n|\eta_2| + nm^2p \left(\frac{p-1}{2} \right) + nm^2p$$

and

$$e_{f_p^*}(1) = n|\varrho_2| + nm^2p \left(\frac{p-1}{2} \right).$$

Because $|\varrho_2| = |\eta_2| + m^2p$, we have $|e_{f_p^*}(0) - e_{f_p^*}(1)| = 0$, which implies that $G_1[G_2]$ is a Legendre cordial graph modulo p . \blacksquare

Theorem 3.6. *Let G_1 and G_2 be connected graphs of orders mp and n , respectively, and suppose that G_2 has size nk . If*

$$|\varrho_1| = |\eta_1| + mk,$$

then the cartesian product graph $G_1 \square G_2$ is a Legendre cordial graph modulo p .

Proof. Let $V(G_2) = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n\}$. Suppose that $f : V(G_1 \square G_2) \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, nmp\}$ is a bijective function defined by

$$f((a, u_j)) = g_1(a) + mp(j - 1), \text{ for } j = 1, 2, \dots, n$$

where $a \in V(G_1)$.

For the edges of the form $(a, u_j)(b, u_j)$ where $ab \in E(G_1)$:

$$f((a, u_j)) + f((b, u_j)) \equiv [g_1(a) + g_1(b)](\text{mod } p)$$

which leads to

$$f_p^*((a, u_j)(b, u_j)) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } ab \in \eta_1 \\ 1 & \text{if } ab \in \varrho_1 \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

for $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

For the remaining edges:

$$f((a, x)) + f((a, y)) \equiv 2g_1(a)(\text{mod } p) \quad (18)$$

where $a \in V(G_1)$ and $xy \in E(G_2)$.

Now, for each $t = 1, 2, \dots, m - 1$ and $xy \in E(G_2)$, let

$$\alpha_t^{xy} = \bigcup_{a \in D_t^1} \{\xi : f((a, x)) + f((a, y)) \equiv \xi(\text{mod } p), 0 \leq \xi < p\}.$$

This expression simplifies to

$$\alpha_t^{xy} = \{0\} \cup \{1, 2, \dots, p - 1\} \quad (19)$$

as a consequence of (18).

From (17) and (19), together with Theorem 2.2, it follows that

$$e_{f_p^*}(0) = n|\eta_1| + nmk \left(\frac{p-1}{2} \right) + nmk$$

and

$$e_{f_p^*}(1) = n|\varrho_1| + nmk \left(\frac{p-1}{2} \right).$$

We observe that $|e_{f_p^*}(0) - e_{f_p^*}(1)| = 0$ as a result of the equality $|\varrho_1| = |\eta_1| + mk$. Therefore, $G_1 \square G_2$ is a Legendre cordial graph modulo p . ■

Theorem 3.7. *Let G_1 and G_2 be connected graphs such that either G_1 or G_2 contains a cycle of odd order. Suppose that G_1 has order np . If*

$$|\varrho_1| = |\eta_1|,$$

then the tensor product graph $G_1 \times G_2$ is a Legendre cordial graph modulo p .

Proof. Note that $G_1 \times G_2$ is a connected graph according to Theorem 2.1. Suppose that $V(G_2) = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_m\}$ and define the bijective function $f : V(G_1 \times G_2) \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, nmp\}$ by

$$f((a, u_j)) = g_1(a) + mp(j - 1)$$

for $j = 1, 2, \dots, m$.

Now, if $ab \in E(G_1)$ and $xy \in E(G_2)$, then $(a, x)(b, y), (b, x)(a, y) \in E(G_1 \times G_2)$, and as a result

$$f((a, x)) + f((b, y)) \equiv f((b, x)) + f((a, y)) \equiv [g_1(a) + g_1(b)] \pmod{p}.$$

As a consequence,

$$f_p^*((a, x)(b, y)) = f_p^*((b, x)(a, y)) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } ab \in \eta_1 \\ 1 & \text{if } ab \in \varrho_1. \end{cases}$$

If G_2 has size q , then we obtain

$$e_{f_p^*}(0) = 2|\eta_1|q \text{ and } e_{f_p^*}(1) = 2|\varrho_1|q.$$

The condition $|\varrho_1| = |\eta_1|$ leads to $|e_{f_p^*}(0) - e_{f_p^*}(1)| = 0$, which shows that $G_1 \times G_2$ is a Legendre cordial graph modulo p . \blacksquare

Theorem 3.8. *Let G_1 and G_2 be connected graphs of orders $3p$ and n , respectively, and suppose that G_1 has size $n - 1$. If*

$$|\varrho_1| = |\eta_1| + 1,$$

then the strong product graph $G_1 \boxtimes G_2$ is a Legendre cordial graph modulo p .

Proof. The proof of this theorem follows by combining the arguments used in the proofs of Theorems 3.6 and 3.7, noting that $E(G_1 \boxtimes G_2) = E(G_1 \square G_2) \cup E(G_1 \times G_2)$. Specifically, by applying the method from the proof of Theorem 3.6, we find that the number of edges in $G_1 \square G_2$ labeled 0 and 1 are

$$n|\eta_1| + 3 \left(\frac{p-1}{2} \right) (n-1) + 3(n-1) \text{ and } n|\varrho_1| + 3 \left(\frac{p-1}{2} \right) (n-1),$$

respectively. Similarly, using the approach from the proof of Theorem 3.7, the number of edges in $G_1 \times G_2$ labeled 0 and 1 are

$$2|\eta_1|(n-1) \text{ and } 2|\varrho_1|(n-1),$$

respectively. Thus,

$$e_{f_p^*}(0) = n|\eta_1| + 3 \left(\frac{p-1}{2} \right) (n-1) + 3(n-1) + 2|\eta_1|(n-1)$$

and

$$e_{f_p^*}(1) = n|\varrho_1| + 3 \left(\frac{p-1}{2} \right) (n-1) + 2|\varrho_1|(n-1).$$

Since $|\varrho_1| = |\eta_1| + 1$, we have $|e_{f_p^*}(0) - e_{f_p^*}(1)| = 1$. Thus, $G_1 \boxtimes G_2$ is a Legendre cordial graph modulo p . \blacksquare

References

- [1] Alameri A. New product binary operations on graphs. *J Sci Technol.* 2016; 21(1): 75–89
doi: 10.20428/jst.v21i1.1016
- [2] Andoyo J. On Legendre cordial labeling of complete graphs. *arXiv, Cornell Univ.* 2025.
doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2509.09528
- [3] Andoyo J, Rulete R. On Legendre cordial labeling of some graphs. *Eur J Math Stat.* 2025; 6(5): 1–7.
doi: 10.24018/ejmath.2025.6.5.409
- [4] Burton DM. *Elementary Number Theory* (7th ed.). McGraw-Hill; 2011.
- [5] Cahit I. Cordial graphs: A weaker version of graceful and harmonious graphs. *Ars Combinatoria.* 1987; 23: 201–207.
- [6] Chartrand G, Zhang P. *Chromatic Graph Theory.* CRC Press; 2009.
- [7] Entero G, Espinola S. On the global distance roman domination of some graphs. *Eur J Pure Appl Math.* 2023; 16(1):44–61
doi: 10.29020/nybg.ejpam.v16i1.4478
- [8] Gallian J. A dynamic survey of graph labeling (25th ed.). *Electron J Combin.* 2022.
Available at: <https://www.combinatorics.org/files/Surveys/ds6/ds6v25-2022.pdf>
- [9] Rosa A. On certain valuations of the vertices of a graph. *Theory of Graphs: Int. Symp.* 1967; 349–355.
- [10] Rosen K. *Elementary Number Theory and its Application* (6th ed.). Addison Wesley, Pearson; 2011.
- [11] Weichsel P. The Kronecker product of graphs. *Proc Amer Math Soc.* 1963; 13: 47–52.